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Ways of development of institutional system of public administration of social security of Ukrainian regions

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Abstract. The paper offers a solution to the scientific problem in the field of science of public management and administration – the substantiation of directions of the development of institutional system of the public social security administration of Ukrainian regions. The present-day institutional system of the public social security administration of Ukrainian regions in the context of its main organizational and functional components were analyzed. With the help of content analysis of the legal base of implementation of these mechanisms of public administration, the scientific approaches to assessment of their effectiveness (typical, methodical, technological) were presented. Using these approaches, it was possible to reveal the range of disadvantages of fundamental laws and regulations in this field. In this regard, the functionality and approaches to the assessment of institutional system of the public social security administration of Ukrainian regions were improved.

1 Introduction

Social security of Ukraine as a constituent of national security is characterized at the current stage of its guaranteeing by a significant influence of external and internal challenges and threats. Institutional sector of this security is also under a significant influence of geopolitical factors and public pressure, as the efficient functioning of this sector has an impact on the level of social and economic state of the whole country and its regions.

Meanwhile, successful functioning of the country's institutional sector depends on the complex provision of social security by it covering both neutralizing and preventive measures in this field at all levels of administration (central and regional). Based on this, it should be noted that it is necessary to study the condition and the peculiarities of complex approach to the institutional public administration in the field of social security.

2 Presenting main material

Some issues of formation of the system of public administration in social field were studied by the following scientists: Yu. Dreval [1], M. Latynin [2], H. Ortina [3], O. Radchenko [4], O. Sydorчук [7] and others. However, there is still a range of

20 November 2020

controversial issues regarding the problem of formation and effective introduction of the institutional system of public administration of social security of regions, so the problematic area under research requires further investigation.

The paper objective is to ground the ways of development of the institutional system of public administration of social security of Ukrainian regions.

The level of regions' development is essential to the economy and sustainable development of any country. In Ukraine, it significantly differs depending on the appearance of one or another index. Determination of indices is based on the available methods of assessment of efficiency of the state's regional policy [5]. Analysis of these methods is based on the determination of complex use of the range of scientific approaches to the assessment of efficiency of Ukraine's regional policy – typical, methodological and technological. The results of the analysis concerning the consideration of these approaches are indicated in the Table 1.

Table 1. Content analysis of the Procedure and Methods of monitoring and assessment of the state's regional policy implementation efficiency

Name of scientific and theoretical approaches	<i>Typical</i>				<i>Methodological</i>			<i>Technological</i>		
	Economic	Targeted	Functional	Social	Organizational	Integrated	Level-based	Time-based	Objective	Subjective
State of their practical introduction through legal establishment	+ (Annex 1 & 2)	+ (cl. 1, cl. 2)	- (cl. 5)	+/- (cl. 5)	+/- (cl. 10)	+/- (cl. 3)	+ (cl. 3, p. 3 cl. 8)	+ (cl. 1, cl. 6)	+/- (cl. 5)	+ (cl. 9)

Source: the table is created based on the analysis of the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine “On Approval of the Procedure and Methods for Monitoring and Assessment of the Efficiency of Regional Policy Implementation” No. 856 dated 21.10.2015 [5]

It was determined that the main defect of institutional provision of public administration of social security of Ukrainian regions is the discrepancy between the indices of their social development used during its annual and quarterly assessment (see Annex 1 and 2 of the analyzed resolution of the CMU [5]). It was found that a wider list of indices should be used for the annual monitoring of efficiency of the state's regional policy implementation than the one that was approved for the quarterly one. Using the special type of diagram (dendrogram), the data of annual monitoring of efficiency of the state's regional policy implementation in 2018 were processed.

The dendrogram was built based on the data of monitoring of efficiency of the state's regional policy implementation in Ukraine, which is carried out in accordance with the resolution of the CMU “On Approval of the Procedure and Methods for Monitoring and

20 November 2020

Assessment of the Efficiency of Regional Policy Implementation” No. 856 dated 21.10.2015 [5]. The dendrogram classifies the regions of Ukraine according to the condition of implementation of this policy.

Type 1 – regions with the least negative value of the indices of efficiency of the state’s regional policy (the city of Kyiv, Kharkiv, Rivne, Vinnytsia and Dnipro regions).

Type 2 – regions with average level of disproportion in the demonstration of indices of efficiency of this policy.

Type 3 – regions with the most negative demonstration of disproportions of indices of efficiency of the state’s regional policy (Donetsk, Luhansk, Mykolaiv, Odesa and Chernihiv regions) (Table 2).

Table 2. Information about annual monitoring of efficiency of the state’s regional policy implementation in Ukraine in 2018 (in comparison with 2017)

Region*	General place of region		Region’s place based on target direction (index)**									
	2017	2018	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
city of Kyiv	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	3	25	2	1	18
Kharkiv	2	2	15	16	7	4	2	5	13	1	8	2
Rivne	3	3	17	10	23	7	14	9	5	18	3	1
Vinnytsia	7	4	9	1	3	6	16	4	20	21	10	5
Dnipro	4	5	3	3	6	3	23	2	6	15	14	8
Chernivtsy	5	6	7	11	19	14	3	7	1	16	2	12
Ternopil	6	7	21	21	8	17	8	13	2	23	7	9
Kyiv	14	8	10	7	10	9	11	1	3	5	21	11
Cherkasy	16	9	16	4	12	8	17	15	14	3	13	15
Poltava	15	10	14	2	15	2	21	17	24	12	11	10
Lviv	9	11	6	9	18	12	13	8	10	17	6	20
Khmelnyskyi	11	12	22	8	16	18	6	14	8	11	12	16
Zhytomyr	12	13	18	13	20	16	15	6	18	19	17	6
Lutsk	10	14	13	19	17	25	9	18	9	22	9	3
Kropyvnytskyi	17	15	20	15	14	24	4	16	7	4	16	14
Ivano-Frankivsk	8	16	8	6	24	15	19	10	15	24	4	13
Sumy	19	17	23	12	9	11	10	23	11	6	15	4
Kherson	18	18	11	23	22	13	5	20	19	10	19	19
Uzhhorod	13	19	2	22	4	23	7	21	4	25	5	24
Zaporizhzhia	20	20	4	14	5	22	24	11	23	14	20	7
Mykolaiv	23	21	12	20	11	20	20	22	12	20	18	21
Odesa	21	22	5	18	21	21	12	12	16	13	22	17
Chernihiv	22	23	19	17	13	19	18	19	17	9	23	25
Donetsk	24	24	24	24	2	5	25	24	25	7	-	22
Luhansk	25	25	25	25	25	10	22	25	21	8	-	23

* – The temporary occupied territories of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea, the city of Sevastopol, and the parts of the temporary occupied territories in Donetsk and Luhansk regions are not taken into account

** – Target direction:

20 November 2020

1. Economic and social unity.
2. Economic effectiveness.
3. Investment and innovation development.
4. Financial self-sufficiency.
5. Development of small and medium business.
6. Labour market effectiveness.
7. Infrastructure development.
8. Availability and quality of educational services.
9. Availability and quality of medical services.
10. Social protection and security.

Source: the table is created based on the data provided by the Ministry for Community and Territory Development [6]

The data indicated in the Table 2 show that during the whole period under review, the city of Kyiv, Kharkiv, Rivne, Vinnytsia and Dnipro regions were the leaders with high indices of regional development. The situation with the development of other regions remains roughly at the same level due to the influence on it (development) of both internal factors (revolutions, unstable domestic situation, reduction of governmental support, energy sources rates growth, unemployment rates increase, etc.) and external factors (reduction of the level of investments in the country's industry, reduction of the level of competitiveness, social and political conflicts, etc.). All this causes destabilization in society, reduction of the level of its security and low efficiency of functioning of the system of public administration. Therefore, it is necessary to insist on the importance of consideration of social exclusion effect, functionalities structuring for the institutional system of public administration, which requires improvement and systematization of its legal and organizational support (Fig. 1).

20 November 2020

Fig. 1. Ways of provision of development of institutional system of public administration of social security of Ukrainian regions

Source: author’s development

We believe that structuring of functionalities of the institutional system of public administration of social administration of Ukrainian regions shall be accompanied by identification of the priority ones, namely “formation,” “orientation,” “coordination,” “stimulation,” “response” and “correction.” It is proved that the functionalities of the first group (“formation” and “coordination”) are determinative, as they deal with the sufficient level of provision of functioning of the subjects (authorities) and the object of public administration (all members of society), as well as their progressive development. The second group of functionalities – “orientation” and “stimulation” – are the managed fields of social development, which deal with the balance of public and private interests in this field, the formation of numerous middle class, the provision of guarantees of social protection of the population, qualitative health protection, etc. Identification of these directions made it possible to prove the importance of the integrated index of secure social development in regions. Deviation from these directions requires the use of the third group of functionalities “response” and “correction,” which stipulates the use of the improved methodological approaches to the assessment of efficiency of functioning of the

20 November 2020

institutional system of public administration of social security of Ukrainian regions. These approaches stipulate the complex determination of the condition of its object and subject development. In this context, the following was achieved:

1) the criteria and methods of annual assessment of the efficiency of implementation of the state's regional policy were specified;

2) they were coordinated with the criteria and methods of its quarterly assessment, etc.

With the purpose of effective use of these approaches, it was offered, on the one hand, to improve the available Procedure and Methods for monitoring and assessment of the efficiency of regional policy implementation, and, on the other hand, to carry out a long-term forecast of secure social development of regions based on the use of the developed simulated model.

3 Conclusions from the conducted research

Thus, the strengthening of social security of Ukrainian regions as an important component of national security is possible under the condition of reasonable implementation of the offered institutional approach to the system of public administration on the qualitatively new complex and conceptual ground. It stipulates the development of legal, organizational, resource, methodological and other support of the institutional system of public administration of social security of regions, its functionalities structuring with simultaneous indication of the priorities, current legislation specification and systematization, as well as the consideration of European values.

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